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Using TRIZ for teaching innovation and creativity

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INTRODUCTION

In the field of engineering education, great emphasis has been posed on developing innovative and appealing curriculum, with a major concern on innovation. Already in

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the 1990, the industry expressed concerns on how traditional engineering education can negatively impact on the creative potential of students and future engineers [1].

This because a lack of creativity represents a constrain in a rapidly changing technology world, while generating new ideas is essential for firms to survive and for social systems to evolve. Companies are increasing competing in no stable arenas and the commercial environment is suggesting that opportunities for innovative designs are accelerating [1]. For management engineering, challenges increase on how to innovate systematically without restricting creativity or overthinking customers' needs [2]. Often, this leads people to reduce the risk of failures by trying to find specific solutions to a problem and not considering the transfer between disciplines that could suggest more innovative solutions [3].

In the last years, creativity has been ranked by both industry and academia as a high desired "best practices" for new graduate engineers. Specifically, creative problem solving, innovation skills and the ability to save costs are recognised as important skills for engineering students. Furthermore, engineers must be able to balance trade offs. Innovative designs and solutions need to be built around conflicting performance parameters, where speed and reliability, quality and cost are acknowledged [1].

For the aforementioned reasons, difficulties in inserting the required skills in engineering studies are clear. Design and innovation processes are full of uncertainty and it is even more difficult to teach the required skills in engineering courses. The call to develop methods, models and theoretical discussions to spur creativity is open among scholars and practitioners. During the years, universities have responded to these calls by adding more design content and introducing more open-ended design problems into their engineering curricula [1].

However, students' curricula that aim to improve problem solving and innovation abilities are still a challenging task for professors when deciding the topics to be included in course programs. This also because cognitive processes such as divergent thinking, working memory, and relational reasoning required for creative problem solving are not well understood [4].

In this setting, the TRIZ methodology, a Russian acronym that stays for Theory of Inventive Problem Solving, represents a method for improving the originality and novelty of the designs generated by engineers and helps to work on the cognitive process afore mentioned [4]. It speeds up the innovation process, by generating an abstraction of systems and provides a systematic approach to analyse problems by using many tools such as the 40 inventive principles, the matrix of contradictions, the laws of technical system evolution and the substance-field analysis. It helps in identifying ways to transfer knowledge between different fields and guides the directions of innovations by establishing a system into which all known solutions can be placed, covering large proportions of physical, chemical and mathematical knowledge-base. This because knowledge is built at different levels of abstraction and it is independent from the specific application field. Moreover, due to its tension towards highly innovative solutions, TRIZ enable to reduce the content/use of Information, Time, Energy, Materials, Space (ITEMS) [5].

Different studies suggest how TRIZ helps to spur student creativity. Empirical studies emphasise the importance of involving engineering students in specialised courses on thinking and problem solving [6]. Moreover, it was found that while TRIZ tends to reduce the number of new ideas of design, they are significantly more innovative than other produced without a structured problem-solving approach [6].

Currently, TRIZ is adopted by universities and companies such as Samsung and Boeing. It has been integrated with other tools, as Function Decomposition Modelling (FDM) or other methods like Axiomatic Design (AD) despite of the different purposes. In addition, TRIZ alternatives arose during the years, as for example OTSM-TRIZ and TOP-TRIZ. Nevertheless, guidelines on how to teach TRIZ within engineering course have not been clearly defined [5].

On these grounds, to answer the research question “how TRIZ can be designed to spur engineering student creativity”, the current work proposes a picture of TRIZ, with a specific focus on education, and its potential exploitation for enriching engineering students’ curricula in innovation. From a review of the literature, we propose and test a framework for teaching TRIZ in engineering courses. Then, we try to verify if the framework follows the line of evolution of TRIZ literature, by adopting a Systematic Literature Network Analysis (SLNA) and a detailed analysis of the keywords. In conclusion, we point out directions of improvement for the proposed framework [7].

1 MATERIAL AND METHODS

In order to develop a framework for using TRIZ in teaching innovation, the methodology followed two main steps.

First, we reviewed the main articles related to TRIZ and TRIZ in education, with the aim to set up a “lean” framework for teaching TRIZ in engineering courses. Starting from the Altshuller’s proposition, we analysed the literature devoted to TRIZ education. We used the Scopus Database to extract all articles and conference papers mainly concerning practical applications of TRIZ in education. This allowed us to identify a framework for teaching TRIZ, that describes the main logical phases and the tools to be proposed. Then, we empirically tested the proposed framework in an international class of students enrolled in an industrial engineering degree, during Innovation Management and New Product Development course. This allowed us to check the feasibility of the proposed framework in a practical setting and detect possible weaknesses of it.

Second, we performed a part of the SLNA methodology, to verify whether the proposed framework is coherent with the evolutionary path of theory on TRIZ in education and to identify opportunities for further improvements. We applied a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to select the most relevant papers on TRIZ and then we analysed them by means of bibliometric tools. After the definition of the scope of analysis, we located the study using as “keywords” TRIZ in abstract, title and keyword of Scopus database. Then, we analysed the abstract of all papers, cleaning from the ones that used TRIZ tool with a different meaning. Then, for the selected papers we identified the strong connected component and we applied bibliographic network tool called Louvain community. It permitted to define the communities where the topic of “education” is present. Then, for the selected communities we used some network visualisation tools for facilitating the investigation. For these communities, we extracted the keywords and their evolution over time and we compared the emerging trends against our proposed framework.

2 TRIZ THEORY AND A PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

Altshuller, the inventor of TRIZ, at the beginning of the XX century tried to structure the knowledge already available within the patents, by pointing out the patterns of technological evolution. Then, it made available this knowledge to all fields, that normally are highly specialized and focused on their own knowledge [8].

He set up a process to govern the creative development of new ideas. Thanks to the patent categorization, he discovered that often different industries, solve similar problems by applying the same principles, that could be reduced to a total of 40 fundamental inventive principles. In this setting, he realized that unsolved problems are matter of unresolved contradictions, in the sense that if the inventor tried to increase a parameter, it will impact negatively on others [8].

Then, Altshuller realized that the innovative solutions should not be found by trying to solve each single problem with a specific solution. The process needs a level of abstraction, where the aim is to identify categories of problems and then work out the “general solution” for each category. Following this reasoning, 4 main phases were suggested by Altshuller: starting with the “specific problem”, people should abstract to the “general problem” and then detail the “general solution”. Only then it is possible to detail the “specific problem” (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Artshuller's TRIZ framework

Several tools have been adopted to teach TRIZ. For example, the contradiction matrix has been usually identified as a tool for generalising problems and the 40 inventive principles are usually associated with the identification of “general solutions”. But “lean” and standard guidelines on how to teach the whole TRIZ process have not been developed yet. Hereafter, in order to answer the research question: how TRIZ can be designed to spur engineering student creativity, we try to build such “lean” approach by a systematic re-

organisation of the main suggestions drawn from the literature and imprinting them on engineering students that own technical skills and analytical abilities.

Starting from the first phase of the TRIZ approach, to identify the “specific problem” of a technology, the literature suggests detailing the Situation Analysis (SA). It aims to question people about the problem perception. On this aspect, students are forced to think about the full system and describe the situation in which the object can be placed. It is a detailed description of the technology entire life, by considering real situations. According to the literature, two different ways can be adopted to describe the technology life, one more structured that accounts for the different functions of the technology [9] and one more qualitative that described the full life of the technology [6]. Moreover, still to detail the specific problem, authors suggest setting up the so-called Method of the Ideal Result (MIR). It is based on the TRIZ concept of the Ideal Ultimate Result (IUR) [10]. This helps in reducing common mistakes made by engineers. It aids users in identifying the available resources and reduce engineers' tendency to introduce additional parts, or elements without having a clear picture of what resources are originally available and without accounting for the new costs that could arise. In this phase, the idea is to conjecture a solution that reduce the amount of information, time, energy, material and space (ITEMS) [6].

For the abstraction of the problem, in order to build up the phase of “problem generalisation”, a relevant and widely used tool is the Substance – Field (Su-Field) Analysis. It permits to translate the description of the SA in a structured abstraction, by translating a complex system to a simple and uniform structure. It is represented by a set of interacting elements. It provides a complete representation of substances and fields that composed or interact with the technology. Different arrows connect the substances and fields, representing the action that occurs between them. It helps in generating ideas and failure analysis [6]. Then, the other main suggested tool to be

used within this phase is the “contradiction matrix”. It lists the most probable design principles to solve a technical contradiction. Specifically, it reports on the rows the feature that needs to be improved and in the columns the feature that will be worsened. Each contradiction is represented by a square in which the principles that would help to identify the solution are listed [1].

Thus, for the identification of a “general solution”, the inventive principles must be adopted [1]. They are generally classified in technical and separation principles. They represent a sort of “recipe” that Altshuller discovered to have been successfully used in more than 20000 patents belonging to several fields of knowledge [6].

Once a general solution is identified, according to the inventive principles, students need to come down to the “specific solution”. According to literature, patents analysis represents the main tool and S-Curve appears to be one of the most adopted tools to have a benchmark with the state of art. It permits to identify the evolutionary status of the technology also in other fields and to understand the feasibility of the solution [9].

Moreover, by reviewing the literature, some authors identified the need to enhance the TRIZ process by recognising also other important phases, such as team building or motivation enhancement [11]. This because often TRIZ is a project-based activity carried out by groups of people, with different skills and backgrounds. To build a cohesively group, authors suggest starting with activities of team building, in order to find strengths and weaknesses of groups. In addition, to motivate students, authors propose to encourage people by means of competition activities [11].

Following these guidelines, a proposed framework for teaching TRIZ in engineering courses, with an active learning approach [12], is characterised by the following phases:

Table 1 Proposed Framework of the TRIZ experimental seminar

Mod.	Aim and Scope	Tool
1	Team building activity and warm up about the technology chosen for the study	Discussion of the chosen technology and Myers Briggs personality test
2	Definition of the “specific problem” by identifying the technology and its distance from the ideality	Situational Analysis, MIR and ITEMS
3	Definition of the “general problem” by mapping the technology functional relationships and its contradictions	Su-Field Analysis and Contradiction Matrix
4	Identification of the “general solution” by using the contradiction matrix, through the “solution triggers”	Inventive and Separation principles
5	Definition of the “specific solution” by studying the technological feasibility and technological benchmark with respect to “the state of art”	Patent analysis (suggest S-Curve Analysis)
6	Competition and commercialization of the technology to a panel of experts in order to evaluate the marketability	Poster and Pitch Presentation

To test the proposed framework, we set up the TRIZ experimental seminar. It was taught in an international class, within the course of Innovation Management and New Product Development. Students were divided into groups of maximum 4 people, for a total of 23 groups. Each group had to choose a product and re-design it by applying the TRIZ methodology. Each lesson lasted 4 hours, for a total of 12 hours, and it mixed theoretical lessons and practical activities. Even theoretical parts were supported by practical examples, to provide students guidelines about the process.

During the first lesson, we focused on the team building activity. Then, we carried out activities related to the definition of the “specific problem” and a first draw of the Su-Field Analysis. During the second lesson, we characterized the “general problem” and we start to implement the “general solution”. During the third lesson, we complete the TRIZ by detailing the “specific solution”.

The evaluation of the seminar was done with a mandatory project. We asked students to report their use of TRIZ to redesign the chosen technology. Moreover, a not mandatory final competition was proposed: students could handle also a pitch and a poster presentation of the improved technology. It would account for a maximum of three more points on the final project mark.

Positive feedback come from the students and university board. The university board decided to fund the project and establish a permanent TRIZ experimental seminar. Students ideated high innovative technological solutions. Nevertheless, often these solutions present a lack of real feasibility, despite of all of them correctly applied the TRIZ tool presented. All the students found difficult to identify the law of evolutions and to collocate the solution with a correct technology intelligence process. Moreover, while they were aware of strengths and weaknesses of the group, sometimes they ended up by splitting the initial group. The final competition to simulate the selling of the technology was enrolled only by 3 groups out of 23.

3 IMPROVEMENTS IN TEACHING TRIZ: SUGGESTIONS FROM A SLNA

Due to the success of the TRIZ experimental seminar and in order to identify avenues for further improvements, we decided to perform a SLNA. This methodology helped us to depict possible enrichment of our experimental seminar and align it with the most recent TRIZ trends. Thanks to the identification of the Louvanian community of the TRIZ citation network, we identified 2 clusters out of 7 concerning education and the engineering topics (see Appendix, Fig. 2). It is worth to notice that education related subjects, also within their specific communities, appear not well linked with the other TRIZ keywords and works.

The first cluster highlights the relation of TRIZ with the problem-solving concept and the technology design. Core concepts appear to be the function analysis of the technology and the use of the contradiction matrix. Suggestions for the improvement of the framework derived from the strong association of TRIZ with the technology life cycle, sustainability and cleaner production. Recent trends highlight the relation of TRIZ with open innovation and the use of computer aid innovation tools (see *Appendix, Fig. 3 and Fig. 4*).

In the second cluster, the TRIZ concept is strongly connected to inventive design, biometrics concepts and patent mining. Substance field appears as a core tool. Within this cluster, interesting suggestions emerge from the relation of TRIZ with notions such as commercialization and sales. Indeed, the customer value and sales related aspects seem to represent a concern of TRIZ. Moreover, TRIZ looks strongly related to topic such as intellectual property (IP), patent or lean. Furthermore, the presence of keywords as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) or the Quality

Function Deployment (QFD) suggest the integration of TRIZ with other tools. Learning platform environments emerge as a widely used support tool. The evolution of the keywords recommends the need of a case-based reasoning approach and the use of TRIZ for enriching curricula (see *Appendix, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6*).

4 CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

The present work has proposed and tested a framework to teach TRIZ in engineering courses. Nowadays problem-solving capacity and creativity are fundamental skills for future engineering curricula. In this setting, TRIZ is a method to spur creativity and the proposed framework is a “lean” guidance on how this tool can be taught to engineering students.

The proposed framework strongly relies on a practical approach, where students have to use the presented tools to improve an existing technology. This choice is coherent with the evidence emerged from the keyword analyses, which bring into evidence that case-based reasoning is one of the best approach to teach TRIZ.

Looking at the empirical test and considering also the paper keywords and their evolution along time, further directions appear relevant for teaching TRIZ and improve the suggested framework for future application in lab settings.

Firstly, TRIZ is highly fitting with other subjects related to engineering studies. TRIZ could be integrated for example with quality related subjects, by joining TRIZ with the QFD. Nevertheless, this integration requires different and complementary skills that must be acquired already within other courses of study. As matter of example, TRIZ should also rely on knowledge related to lean approaches, IT and optimization that could be important to design “stronger” TRIZ solutions. This confirms the relevance that TRIZ could have in a curriculum also because it offers possibilities to exploit and integrate different fields of engineering. An interfaculty seminar of different engineering fields would be an opportunity to improve TRIZ results, because of different skills and backgrounds to be exploited. Secondly, prerequisites and knowledge in terms of patents and IP come out as necessary to implement innovative and feasible technology solutions. This suggests reflecting on the importance of introducing IP related topics in engineering courses. Thirdly, a strong attention should be given to eco-innovation and sustainability uses of TRIZ. In this direction, teachers should encourage the study of technology regarding the development of eco-sustainable products. Fourthly, TRIZ is highly scalable with an open innovation (OI) approach. On these grounds, different phases of TRIZ could include the presence of experts, with different backgrounds. This would help student in analysing the feasibility of their technology. Students would have the opportunity to meet people from the working world, giving new perspectives to innovative didactic in terms of involvement of practical experiences and not only academic competences. Fifthly, TRIZ could be implemented with more engaging and dynamic learning environments. For example, it can be used within learning platforms. By using these tools, classes of different universities of the world could participate to the TRIZ project in order to provide more interesting solution. Moreover, also experts would be more easily engaged to participate to a TRIZ experimental seminar. Lastly, the TRIZ framework should be more linked with market aspects and a strong focus on the client. In our empirical test, only few students participated to the “market” competition, despite of the extra points. In a total OI approach, the possibility to talk with experts and the chance to receive feedback from a sample of possible clients already when applying the TRIZ process would help students in improving the launch into the market of the new designed technology.

The paper presents also some limitations. The proposed framework was tested only for one year and in a class of mainly industrial engineers. We aim to test the proposed framework the next years and to enlarge the sample to other engineering faculties or see how it could also be used in workplaces with entrepreneurial goals. In addition, the TRIZ experiment was not been compared with other works on idea generation and concept definition that not adopt the TRIZ methodology. We aim to compare the results with our previous project that not adopt TRIZ and report statistics for example on the degree of inventiveness and on the final mark of the project. Lastly, the keyword analysis provides a real broad overview of the main and most recent concepts concerning TRIZ. Nevertheless, an in deep analysis of each paper would allow to have a more punctual understanding of the topic and its evolution.

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APPENDIX

Fig. 2. Louvain Communities

Fig. 3. VoSViewer Keyword depiction of the first community

Fig. 6. VoSViewer Keyword depiction of the second community